

Quantum Spin and Information

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In a previous note (1), we argued that information in an equilibrium situation is linked to degeneracy of information. For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, $\ln(\exp(-e/T))$ where $e=pp/2m$, this is proportional to e the information. For two body collisions, information degeneracy is associated with any $e_i+e_j=E$ having the same product probability $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ (both for reactants and products). For a quantum bound state, we argued that there are two probabilities for a particle, $a(p)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ with a wavefunction formed by $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Only the latter is linked to information i.e. $\ln(\exp(ipx)) = ipx$ with p being information. The degeneracy is only seen when p collides in an impulse manner with the potential $V(x)=\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ i.e. $\exp(ip_i x) \exp(i k_j x)$ where $p_i+k_j = P$ yields a degenerate produce probability.

In this note, we wish to consider the case of spin which is similar to that of a fixed angular momentum. For a fixed angular momentum l , one has quantized projections along any axis of $-l$ to l in steps of one. The degeneracy is based on the idea that any axis has the same set of projections. Unlike the MB classical gas and momentum in a quantum bound state, the degeneracy in angular momentum appears without explicitly considering any interaction. Furthermore, this degeneracy ensures that three-space is defined physically because one may measure projections along x,y,z . For momentum, even with p_x,p_y,p_z one may shift the z axis to lie along the momentum vector. The information from $\ln(\exp(im \phi)) = im \phi$ is m the angular momentum projection.

The idea of three-space being defined by angular momentum seems to carry over to the photon where E (electric field) and B (magnetic field) are perpendicular and define a plane perpendicular to the physical momentum direction. There is degeneracy in the location of the E field (information degeneracy) and so circularly polarized light represents energy $(.5E|E| + .5B|B|)$ moving in a circle.

The Klein-Gordon equation deals with scalars because momentum may be thought of as being in one direction. If one wishes to impose the idea of three-space, then one may create a linear equation using $s_x p_x + s_y p_y + s_z p_z$ where s_x,s_y,s_z are Pauli matrices. It seems that it is the spin which defines three-space as the z axis may always be oriented along the direction of momentum, but spin projections may always be found along any axis x,y,z (although one at a time). Degeneracy is present because one may always find spin projections along any axis.

Thus, it seems that internal motion within an electron follows the same ideas of information degeneracy as a signature of equilibrium as angular motion (created through an external interaction i.e. $V(r)$). This idea of equilibrium through information degeneracy (i.e. quantum mechanics) seems to extend to a lower level than the Schrodinger equation or Klein-Gordon equation because it is only through linearizing the latter for a free particle that one sees spin emerge.

Angular Momentum, Spin and Three Space

In classical physics in three-space, angular momentum may involve motion confined to a plane i.e. two dimensions. In quantum mechanics in three-space, any fixed angular momentum is

associated with three dimensions because one may choose any axis in three-space to use for the quantized projections which take values from $-l$ to l in steps of 1. Thus, it seems the presence of angular momentum in quantum mechanics physically defines three-space. Momentum may have values p_x, p_y, p_z , but one may choose a new z axis along the direction of the momentum vector. Then the motion appears as one dimensional. The free particle Klein-Gordon equation reflects this one dimensional behaviour by linking energy to the magnitude of momentum (squared) which is a scalar. Free motion is one direction and so there is a degeneracy in this sense, but no sense of three-space. If one decides to linearize the Klein-Gordon equation, matrices s_i appear linked to the three axes i.e. $s_x p_x + s_y p_y + s_z p_z$. (Actually in the Dirac case 4×4 matrices appear with the Pauli matrices s_i being contained within these.) It is the matrices s_i which seem to be linked to three-space and define this space as one may find projections of spin along any axis, just as in the case of angular momentum.

Unlike angular momentum which results from an interaction with a potential $V(r)$, spin appears to be an intrinsic property of an electron or nucleon etc. It is, however, very similar to angular momentum in its information degeneracy behaviour.

Spin and Information

We argue that the degeneracy of the axis used to measure the projections of spin or angular momentum is linked to the idea of information degeneracy found in equilibrium, in this case the equilibrium called quantum mechanics. In (1), we argued that in a classical Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, information degeneracy is linked to $\ln(\exp(i e/T))$ where $e = p^2/2m$. For two colliding particles in a gas in equilibrium, the product probability $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ for any $e_i + e_j = E$ is the same. This holds for the colliding particles and the product. Thus we argue that information degeneracy is a signature of equilibrium.

In quantum mechanics we suggested that in a quantum bound state there are two probability factors i.e. $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ with the wavefunction being $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Only the second $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with information $\ln(\exp(ipx)) = ipx$ or p momentum. To see degeneracy one must consider the interaction between a quantum particle's momentum probability $\exp(ipx)$ and $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. The equilibrium degeneracy enters through:

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is the factor of $\exp(ipx)$ if one takes the Schrodinger equation and writes $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as Fourier series. Any $V_k a(p-k)$ yields an $\exp(ipx)$ and so there is information degeneracy. ((1)) shows how this degeneracy establishes a resonance or equilibrium. $a(p)$ is also part of probability, but not linked to information. In classical physics there is only one probability e.g. the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor which is real $\exp(-e/T)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is imaginary because one cannot discern p at x , as $\exp(ipx)$ is always interacting with $V_k \exp(ikx)$.

In both the classical MB gas and the quantum bound state described in terms of $\exp(ipx)$, an interaction is linked to information degeneracy. Angular momentum l also appears in a quantum bound state with $V(r)$, but there is no explicit degeneracy emerging from a collision. Rather it is the projections of a fixed l which demonstrate the degeneracy of information:

$\ln(\exp(i m \phi))$ proportional to m information ((2))

The reason that momentum requires a $\sum_k \exp(ikx)$ probability term for information (p) degeneracy to be visible is that quantum bound states (we argue) are based on impulse hits. Momentum changes during such hits. It is possible, however, to have a set of $\exp(ipx)$ terms with weights $a(p)$, i.e. the wavefunction, represent a resonance as it does for bound solutions. Given that one may not discern a specific p at a given x , which we argue is the reason for the complex probability $\exp(ipx)$, one may not discern specific angular motion at any given point either (say angle). In such a case, one is left with a degeneracy, namely that of the rotational axis even for the case of a one angular momentum l resonance (wavefunction). This has far reaching consequences as one may measure a projection of l along any axis (one at a time). One then has information about a projection about this one axis. A second measurement yields information about a projection about itself, but information about the first projection is lost. We argue that the degeneracy of the projection axis is that associated with the information m needed for an equilibrium state.

In the case of spin, there is no visible interaction with a potential as in the case of angular momentum yet similar mathematics in terms of matrices (groups) arise. As a result, $J=L+S$ is often used to combine regular L angular momentum with S spin. Spin may also be measured along any axis (one at a time) and is an intrinsic property of a particle (e.g. electrons and nucleons have spin $1/2$). As a result, it seems there may be an internal quantum mechanical equilibrium within say an electron or nucleon which gives rise to information degeneracy m i.e. the projection of spin along any axis. Even though one does not use the Schrodinger equation to find spin and its projection as one does for angular momentum, it appears by forcing three-space recognition into the free particle Klein-Gordon equation.

Conclusion

In (1) we argued that information degeneracy was a signature of equilibrium for both the classical gas and quantum bound state. In the classical case, $\ln(\exp(-e/t))$ is proportional to e , the information, and $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ is the same for any $e_i+e_j=E$. For a quantum bound state described in terms of momentum states, the interaction is not two body collisions, but collisions with $V(x)=\sum_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus, there are two factors of probability $a(p)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ yielding a wavefunction $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Only the second factor is linked to information with $\ln(\exp(ipx))$ proportional to p . Degeneracy occurs through $\sum_p p^2/m a(p) + \sum_k \exp(ikx) a(p-k) = a(p) E$. Any $\sum_k \exp(ikx) a(p-k)$ combination produces an $\exp(ipx)$. This we argue is the information degeneracy in the quantum equilibrium.

In this note, we consider the case of a three-space quantum bound particle with a fixed angular momentum. We first note that unlike classical physics in which such motion may be in a fixed plane because one may follow the particle's p at any x , in quantum mechanics one cannot. In such a case a fixed l has a degeneracy related to its spin axis. Given that $Y(l,m) [\theta, \phi]$ is a wavefunction solution (i.e. an equilibrium resonance) we argue that the information, $\ln(\exp(i m \phi))$ proportional to m , has degeneracy linked to the projection axis. Furthermore, this degeneracy ensures that three-space is physically defined because projections of angular momentum may be found along x,y,z or any axis. Momentum of a free particle on the other hand

may be taken to lie along a single axis. This has implications for the free particle Klein-Gordon equation which only deals with the magnitude of momentum (squared). This magnitude may be thought of as lying along one axis. If one insists on sensing three-space then one is forced to linearize the Klein-Gordon equation which leads to constraint matrices (unitary matrices). It is these matrices which are linked to three dimensions and have projections along any axis. Thus, they are linked to information degeneracy. In the case of spin, however, which is an intrinsic property of a particle, this seems to suggest that internal motion within the particle (say an electron or nucleon) follows the same information degeneracy ideas that are found in the Schrodinger equation with angular momentum. As a result, L and S are combined to form J because they both represent angular motion, although a kind of angular motion which is very different from that of classical physics for which one may follow a particle noting its p_x, p_y, p_z at every x, y, z .

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Product Probability in Quantum Mechanics with One Factor Linked to Maximum Entropy and Information (preprint, zenodo, 2021)